

Attendance Registration Agency Employees Empower Women, Child Protection and Family Planning

Dovi Septiari^{a*}, Nisa Fakhriatul Filzah^b

^a*Jurusan Manajemen Bisnis, Politeknik Negeri Batam, dovi@polibatam.ac.id, Indonesia*

^b*Jurusan Manajemen Bisnis, Politeknik Negeri Batam, filzah.bieber@gmail.com, Indonesia*

Abstract. Women Empowerment, Child Protection and Family Planning do not have sufficient attendance, it is seen from the problems that occur in the institution. The problem is that the manual attendance recording can cause the presence of data manipulation, recording attendance is usually carried out by the foreman and supervised by the head of the production in order to avoid manipulation of attendance data. Based on research conducted by the authors of recording employee attendance BP3AKB Batam, the results obtained are employee attendance data collection process manually is quite difficult. Part staffing should note and record employee attendance manually which takes a lot, not effective because it uses a lot of paper. Vulnerable fraud or manipulation of attendance data. Possible solutions to the problems that occur in the institution is replacing of absent manually into finger print, ID barcode and other systems, increased waste paper and automatic budget spent for the purchase of paper also grew, forming part which oversees attendance and absences are placed near with the regulatory body to prevent further fraud.

Keywords: recording attendance, attendance manipulation data

Introduction

Human resource issues are still in the spotlight, and the foundation for the company to continue to survive in the era of globalization. Human resources are the critical success factors of effective implementation of the organization, although supported by infrastructure and redundant power sources. Without the support of reliable human resource and have optimum performance the company's activities will not be resolved properly. With the employment of human resources play an important role in the organization because in human resources has a very strategic position as executor of management functions such as planning, organizing, staffing, leadership, control, supervision, and implementation of the operational organization.

Literature Review

The procedure is a clerical activity, usually involving several people within a department or be made to ensure uniform handling corporate transactions that occur repeatedly.

Employee Data Processing Procedures

Employee data processing procedures in Women Empowerment, Child Protection and Family Planning Batam are

1. Employees received an employee of Personnel and Training Agency (PTA).
2. PTA received an employee that has been filled by the employee, then BKD check form, if not complete,

*Corresponding author. E-mail: dovi@polibatam.ac.id

the form is returned to the employee and when complete it will record PTA employees.

3. PTA then will archive the form of employee data.

4. PTA make reports employee data and give it to leader.

5. Leader receive report employee data and then verify it, then report employee data has been verified that gets returned PTA.

6. Parts of PTA received reports employee data has been verified by the head, and then saved into archive of reports and employee.

Management report

The personnel office make a report to management on:

1. Statistics employee turnover.
2. Statistics dismissal of employees.
3. Rates of wages in similar industries.
4. Rates of local wages.
5. The ability of employees.

Time eeping procedures

The work of recording time can basically be divided into two parts, namely the present time recording and time recording work, are

1. Attending Time Recording Procedures
2. Working Time Recording Procedures

Form used in time keeping

Form used in recording time are

1. Note the time attendance
2. The record of working time

Time Recording Equipment

Various tools timekeeper are

1. Attendance time recorder
2. Job time recorder
3. Time Stamps
4. Hours guidelines for monitoring time

Results and Discussion

Attendance Recording Still Can Cause Manual Data manipulation Presence. BP3AKB also have attendance/absences.

Attendance owned by BP3AKB still manually, so that there are weaknesses in the institution. Weakness manual attendance at the institution is:

1. The data collection process manually employee attendance list is quite complicated. Personnel department should record and record employee attendance manually which take some time lots.

2. Vulnerable fraud or manipulation of attendance data.

Based on the observations made by the authors for carrying out the process of industrial apprenticeship at BP3AKB, there has been a fraud committed by employees. One form of fraud committed by employees in BP3AKB is the discrepancy between the attendance time records and records of working time. Here the author will give one example of a form of cheating, one example would be the authors explain in this discussion is based on real events that occurred in BP3AKB. "Employee A, was not present at the previous day for something or another, but absenteeism A day was not recorded in the attendance, because no officer or employee specifically responsible for overseeing the recording of attendance and record employee absence on that day, so the next day the employee A can fill the absent and attendance information on the previous day.

Based on the above it can be seen that BP3AKB not have attendance was good, but absenteeism will be used as the basis for calculating the salaries of employees so that the required attendance was good in order that employees get a salary that is appropriate based on the presence and the duties and responsibilities that have been done.

Conclusion

Based on the discussion that has been described in Chapter VI, the authors conclude that BP3AKB does not have a section that oversees employee absenteeism, besides BP3AKB also do not have any initiatives or plans to replace the absent using the Finger Print or attendance device, other than the recording attendance performed by the company is still not effective. The attendance done by the company is:

1. Attendance carried out without supervision by a supervisor or personnel department

2. The reported absences to the treasurer were used as the basis for calculating salaries. Attendance is reported is absenteeism done without supervision, so that an employee is late, employees who deliberately

do not attendance or in other words, an employee who has been manipulating absent will not be liable to pay cuts and other.

Based on the discussion and conclusions that have been outlined above, the writer can convey the suggestion that BP3AKB should have a section that oversees employee absences that incident as an example in the above discussion does not occur. According Baridwan (1991), recording the attendance is usually done by a foreman and supervised by the head of production. BP3AKB must also improve attendance, if possible, the agency should immediately replace the manual attendance with attendance using the Finger Print and others.

References

- Baridwan, Z. (1991). *Sistem Akuntansi*. Yogyakarta: BPFE-YOGYAKARTA.
- Sunyoto, D. (2002). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: CAPS (Center for Academic Publishing Service).